

success story

> **Pilot 5: Disaster
Resilience >
Drought, forest
fire & pest risk
assessment**

**Regional |
National Scale**

A new fire index to assess the benefits of fuel management in reducing the risk of fire in Finland

A newly-developed fire danger index the fire occurrence probability Index (FOPI) aims at enhancing fire danger predictions in environments where fuel is limited and where fire risk is influenced by the rapid drying of intermittent fuel. This is achieved by combining the widely-used Canadian fire weather index (FWI) with GEOS observations of vegetation optical depth (VOD) from ESA's SMOS mission, serving as an indicator of fuel quantity and moisture.

The index was developed in a collaborative work between ECMWF and ESA to help assess the impact of fuel on the probability of fire occurrence. The index will be tested with in EIFFEL project pilot 5 to assess the benefits of nature-based solutions, such as forest cleaning and fuel management, to the fire risk in Finland.

ESA article:

https://www.esa.int/Applications/Observing_the_Earth/FutureEO/SMOS/Forecasting_fires_with_SMOS

Image: ESA

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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